

D4.1 – REPORT ON THE NANOPILLAR BIOCOMPATIBILITY

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Abstract:	<p>This document summarizes the initial series of biocompatibility tests concluded on living tissues and cells cultured on flat surfaces, which are intended for holding the nanopillars of the StretchBio prototype. We present the preliminary findings regarding cell survival and potential toxicity of the materials and surfaces, which will be utilized throughout the entire project. Our results indicate that various cell types and tissues can be successfully cultured in direct contact with the surfaces intended for nanopillar fabrication. We affirm that these materials are biocompatible and thus serve as a suitable foundation for the proposed device architecture in StretchBio.</p>

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Executive Summary

The primary objective of the StretchBio project is to design, develop, fabricate and validate an advanced label-free and compact nanosystem for continuously monitoring and quantifying mechanical stresses in “ex vivo” fresh tissue biopsies. The initial step towards achieving this goal involved testing the biocompatibility of living tissues and cells, as well as assessing tissue and cell survival when cultured on various planar surfaces. This was carried out prior to testing the biocompatibility of the nanopillars structures. This deliverable provides a summary of the initial work conducted in this area during the first year of the project.

Several cell lines (Caco-2, lung cancer cell lines, and S2 cells from *Drosophila*), epithelial tissues from *Drosophila* (wing imaginal discs), and tumour sections from fresh biopsies of surgical lung cancer patients were seeded on different nanodevice surfaces to test cell/tissue biocompatibility. Additionally, nanosurfaces were coated with various extracellular matrix proteins and adhesion molecules to determine whether they improve viability compared to standard cell/tissue procedures.

Thus, we compared cell viability on nanodevice surfaces with the well-established cell culture conditions to each cell/tissue type used. None of the tested cell lines exhibited increased mortality when seeded on the nanodevice surface. Furthermore, *Drosophila* imaginal discs remained viable for several hours after being culture on different materials. Similarly, thin sections from tumour biopsies exhibited good survival on the nanodevice surface. However, when cultured on nanopillars, both lung cancer cell lines and *Drosophila* imaginal discs epithelia showed a stress response after a certain period.

The work reported here demonstrates promising results towards achieving the objectives described in the project, and do not envisage any critical aspect that could jeopardize the main goal to be pursued in the next stages of StretchBio. Over the next few months, we will evaluate the biocompatibility of the future devices and fabricated pillars, as well as the ability of cells and tissues to attach to the devices and maintain their viability.

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1. Purpose of the document

This deliverable summarises the effort made to assess the biocompatibility of living tissue with nanopillars and their survival on various substrates, some of which include nanopillars. Here, we analyse different cell lines and tissues to test their biocompatibility with the surfaces of the future project devices. Full details of the experimental methods are provided in the annex of the deliverable.

2. Related documents

This deliverable builds upon the findings derived from the initial stages of WP4, and it will serve as a reference point for the other deliverables within this work package. The conclusions outlined in Deliverable *D1.3 - OEI – Requirement No.12* remain valid, and no ethical concerns associated with the actions described herein have been identified.

3. Results

As a first approach, we examined the cellular response and interaction with flat Si-related substrates to assess their biocompatibility and determine the suitable materials for the nanopillars for the final device. The list of substrates is listed here:

Planar Substrates
Si n-type
Si p-type
SiO ₂ 303,4nm
SiO ₂ 962nm
Processed Si

Table 1: Substrates employed for biocompatibility assays.

Biocompatibility assumes significant importance in the development of nanopillars with the ultimate goal of integrating them with biological cells and tissues. Both silicon (Si) and Silicon dioxide (SiO₂) are widely employed in materials for biological testing and bioengineering due to their known biocompatibility [1]. However, certain biological hazards have been associated with Si-containing materials. The evaluation of SiO₂ nanoparticle toxicity and biocompatibility has yielded controversial results in the literature, mainly due to the lack of standardized procedures and insufficient characterization of nanomaterials in biological systems [2]. For instance:

- 1) Studies have demonstrated the generation of free Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) upon exposure to SiO₂, with a strong correlation observed between decreased cell viability and increased levels of ROS [3].
- 2) The surface of SiO₂ substrates has been found to respond to pH stimuli and salt concentration, while silane groups on the SiO₂ surface can interact with biological molecules [4].

Due to the potential variation in the biological response to Si and SiO₂ depending on the cell type, we used various cell lines and tissues to evaluate their biocompatibility. All cell lines were grown as monolayers. The list of substrates is listed here:

Cell/tissue type	Origin	Description
Caco-2	Human colonic adenocarcinoma	Model of intestinal drug studies. Easy to handle, reproducible.
A-594	Human lung adenocarcinoma	<i>In vitro</i> model of lung cancer, retain human alveolar basal epithelial cells. 2D cell model before study patient's tumour biopsies
NCI-H358	Human bronchioloalveolar carcinoma	Non-small cell carcinoma of the lung harbouring KRAS mutation. <i>In vitro</i> model of lung cancer. 2D cell model before study patient's tumour biopsies
S2 cells	<i>Drosophila</i>	Derived from a primary culture of <i>Drosophila</i> embryos. This cell line has been used for studies on control, tumorigenesis, and regeneration
Imaginal discs	<i>Drosophila</i>	Larval epithelial discs. Perform viability/Adhesion studies before to human samples.
Lung tumour samples	Human	Tumour samples from patients

Table 2: Cell types and tissues utilized in this study.

a. Tests on cell lines

Caco-2 cells, also known as human colonic adenocarcinoma cell line, serve as extensively employed models in intestinal drug studies pharmaceutical research [5]. Consequently, we conducted biocompatibility assays on this cell type with the intention of utilizing them as a model for drug high-throughput screening cells in the future operational devices.

NCI-H358 and A-549 cell lines are derived from lung cancer patients and serve as *in vitro* models for lung cancer tumours. Prior to testing tumour samples from humans, toxicokinetic and pharmacokinetic studies can be conducted on these cell lines.

S2 Cells and tissues from *Drosophila* have been extensively utilized as a model system for various studies, including growth control, tumorigenesis and regeneration [6].

Typically, *in vitro* cells growth necessitates an additional protein coating on the surface where they will be seeded. In our study, we employed various extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins:

Cell type	Extracellular matrix protein for coating	Final Concentration of ECM protein
Caco-2	Collagen type I, rat tail	1,1µg/ml
A-549 and NCI-H358	Gelatine	1%
A-549 and NCI-H358	Matrigel	0,3 mg/ml
S2 cells	Poly-L-Lysine	0,1mg/ml

Table 3: Overview of tested extracellular matrix protein coatings to determine optimal cell culture conditions on diverse surface materials.

We deemed a material to be cytotoxic if it resulted in a reduction of cell viability by 30%, in accordance with ISO 10993-5 guidelines for biological testing [7].

Figure 1: Illustration of the biocompatibility values for the evaluated planar substrates and the control group (no substrate) following 6-days of culture with the Caco-2 cell line. Collagen, commonly used for the standard seeding procedure of the Caco-2 cell line, served as the extracellular matrix protein. The data is presented as the mean of viable cells \pm SD. The red line denotes the median lethal dose, indicating 30% cell mortality.

Figure 2. Viability assays of A-549 and NCI-H358 cells on planar substrates. a) Viability assay of the A-549 cell line demonstrated no discernible differences between coated and non-coated for all tested substrates. b) Cultured NCI-H358 cells exhibited no significant variations between different surfaces, both with and without coating. Data are represented as mean of viable cells \pm SD.

Figure 3: Viability of S2 cells on planar surfaces. Up) Fluorescence images of S2 cells after 2 days of culture on different substrates (image magnification x200). Each blue dot represents a cell nucleus. Down) Average number of cells counted at five different points for each substrate. No significant differences were observed in the number of cells among the tested substrates (mean of viable cells \pm SD).

No significant differences in viability were observed for any cell type used in this study when seeded on different substrates, regardless of whether the substrates were coated or non-coated.

Following the evaluation of various planar surfaces, viability assays were conducted on nanopillars:

Nanopillars surface
Processed Si, etched for 5'
Processed Si, etched for 7'

Table 4: Nanopillars utilized in viability assays.

Figure 4: Viability assays of A549 cells (A and B) and NCI-H358 cells (C and D) on nanopillars. Assays revealed 100% cell viability after 5 days of seeding (red square denotes nanopillar location) (image magnification x40).

Lung cancer cell lines, A-549 and NCI-H358 exhibited 100% viability after 5 days of culture when seeded on nanopillars.

ROS levels were measured in cells cultured on substrates containing nanopillars arrays in specific regions. Figure 5 demonstrates that the NCI-H358 cell line displayed greater sensitivity when cultured on nanopillars, exhibiting statistically significant levels of ROS compared to cells cultured on a control surface (plastic). In the A-549 cell line, increased levels of ROS were detected after just 5 hours of culture (Figure 5).

Although lung cell lines cultured on nanopillars demonstrated an increase of ROS levels, viability remained unaffected. This indicates that while there was ROS expression (Figure 5), the levels were not sufficiently high to impact cell viability. Quantification of live cells cultured on nanopillars devices, in comparison to control surfaces, revealed no significant differences across all analysed lung cancer cell lines (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 5: ROS levels of cells cultured on nanopillars. (* $p > 0,05$, ** $p > 0,01$, *** $p > 0,0001$), (mean \pm SD) (TBPH= tert-Butyl hydroperoxide was used as a positive control of ROS).

Figure 6: Viability assay of A-549 cells. The assay conducted on A-549 cells revealed no significant differences between viability of cells observed on a plastic surface compared to cells grown on nanopillars. No substantial cell death was observed. The right image demonstrates that cells are viable and attached to the nanopillars.

Figure 7: Viability assay conducted on NCI H358 cells. The assay conducted on NCI H358 cells revealed no significant differences between viability of cells observed on a plastic surface compared to cells grown on nanopillars. No substantial cell death was observed. The right image demonstrates that cells are viable and attached to the nanopillars, although they did not achieve complete confluence.

b. Tests on imaginal discs

To assess the impact of different substrate materials on the viability of *Drosophila* tissue, TREDsRED imaginal discs were cultured on two types of nanopillars (Processed Si 5' and Processed Si 7') as well as on a glass slide as a control.

Initially, levels of oxidative stress in the tissues were comparable across all three conditions for up to 7 hours of culture (Figure 8A). However, for longer culture durations, the discs exhibited a stress response only when cultured on the Processed Si 7' sample. It is worth noting that after 24 hours, stress levels increased in general across all conditions, likely due to the prolonged culture period. It is known that wing imaginal discs can be cultured under optimal conditions for up to 18 hours after dissection [8].

Figure 8: A) Mean pixel values of the TREDsRED fluorescence at various time points. The data illustrates a noticeable stress-inducing effect of the Processed Si 7' substrate on the imaginal disc after 7 and 24 hours of culture. B) Maximum pixel value projection of imaginal discs carrying the TREDsRED transgene (dotted line) after 24 h of culture (from left to right: No substrate, Processed Si 5', Processed Si 7').

c. Tests on biopsies

As an initial step in evaluating the biocompatibility between tumour tissue and nanopillars, we employed an *ex-vivo* model using thin sections of fresh tumour biopsies obtained from surgical non-small cell lung (NSCLC) patients and placed them on the surface of the nanopillars.

Qualitative analysis of haematoxylin-eosin (H&E) images indicated that overall architecture of the tumour was preserved after 48 hours of culture on the nanopillar device. Tumour sections were subjected to standard histologic procedures, including staining 5 μm sections with H&E to

assess tissue integrity, and using the proliferation marker Ki-67 to analyse cancer cell proliferation.

Moreover, quantitative image analysis was conducted using QuPath [9] to evaluate the density of cancer cells (based on H&E images) and the density of Ki-67-positive cancer cells in the tumour fragments placed on the nanopillar device. These density values were then compared with those obtained from control conditions. The density values obtained from the tumour fragments on the device fell within the range observed in the control experiments, affirming that the tumour fragments obtained from fresh biopsies remained functional and viable on the nanopillar device for at least 48 hours (Figure 9B).

Figure 9: A) Representative images of Non-small lung cancer tumour sections cultured on top of the nanopillars Si substrate. The top images show sections stained with H&E, while the bottom images display staining for KI-67. B) Plots depicting the quantification of cancer cell density (top) and KI-67 nuclear density (bottom) from lung cancer tumour sections cultured in the pre-optimized conditions and on top of the device.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable builds upon the initial findings of WP4 in the StretchBio project: the main objective was to investigate the biocompatibility of various Si and SiO₂ substrates at the cellular and tissue levels, with the aim of early identifying potential viability problems in later stages of the project and defining the optimal material for fabricating the nanopillar-based devices proposed in the grant agreement.

To achieve this, we conducted cell viability experiments on planar surfaces to assess their impact on cell morphology, phenotype, and function. The cell lines (Caco-2, A-549, NCI-H358, and S2) and tissues (*Drosophila* imaginal discs and human lung tumour samples) used in this study exhibited similar viability regardless of the substrate material or treatment tested, and there were no notable differences between coated and non-coated surfaces.

When cells are cultured on nanopillars, they also exhibit good viability since they can adapt by altering their shape and adhesion properties based on the geometry, dimensions, and spacing between neighbouring structures as already reported in the literature [10].

In lung cancer cell lines, we observed increased stress levels, indicated by elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Additionally, for *Drosophila* imaginal discs, the Processed Si 7' substrate appeared to have a detrimental effect over longer culture periods. However, these stress levels were not sufficiently high to impact cell viability.

Likewise, the viability and functionality of thin tumour fragments obtained from a surgical lung cancer patient and placed on the material surface were comparable to those achieved using a standard ex-vivo protocol involving placing tumour fragments on a Transwell® for up to 48 hours. These findings validate the results obtained from cell lines and *Drosophila* tissues and confirm that the StretchBio substrates are suitable for sustaining the viability of patient biopsies.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that, for the ultimate purpose of the project, the different materials tested (Si and SiO₂) can be utilized as a platform for tissue culture without concerns regarding the viability of biological samples. Furthermore, no significant and fundamental issues regarding the biocompatibility of tissues and cells that could jeopardize the StretchBio project have been identified at this stage.

5. References

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6. Glossary

Acronym	Term
D	Deliverable
ECM	Extracellular matrix
H&E	Haematoxylin-eosin
NSCLC	Non-small cell lung cancer
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
SD	Standard Deviation
Si	Silicon
SiO ₂	Silicon dioxide
WP	Work package

Annex 1: Supplemental Material and Methods

This section provides a detailed description of the methods employed to achieve the aforementioned results.

Cell lines culture

The cell culture reagents maintain the pH of the culture medium in equilibrium under the standard condition, which involve a 5% CO₂ environment in humidified air at 37°C, within the cell culture incubator.

Caco-2 cell line

Caco-2 cells were cultured in D-MEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 1mM glutamine and 1U/ml penicillin/streptomycin at 37°C and 5%CO₂ conditions, until confluence. Before cell seeding, the substrates were placed on 24-well plates (Falcon® 24-well Clear Flat Bottom TC-treated Culture Microplate) as indicated in Figure 1. Twelve wells for each plate were previously coated with 100 µL of collagen 1.1µg/ml (Collagen type I, Rat tail, Stock: 4.4mg/ml) for 1h at 37°C and 5% CO₂, and after that, 75000 Caco-2 cells/cm² were seeded on the top of the different substrates or on the well surface with 300 µL of cell culture medium. After 48 hours in culture, cell medium was changed and incubated for additional 72h at 37°C and 5% CO₂, until a complete monolayer was observed in a phase contrast microscope. Each experimental condition had two replicates and data were the result for three independent experiments.

At the end of this period (day 6 of culture), the number of viable cells were assayed by means of the Alamar Blue cell viability reagent according to the manufacturer's protocol, and subsequent reading at 530 nm and 590 nm of excitation and emission wavelength, respectively. This reagent is a ready-to-use resazurin-based solution that functions as a cell health indicator by using the reducing power of living cells to quantitatively measure viability.

Statistical analyses were performed using a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a Tukey's post-hoc test to make comparisons between each group. Significance is indicated in the figures only when P<0.05, as follows: *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0,001.

NCI-H358 and A-549 cell lines

NCI-H358 cells were cultured in RPMI1640 medium supplemented with 10% of FBS. 42000 cells/cm² were seeded in each well of the 24 well-plate including the different tested devices. A-549 cells were cultured in D-MEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS, and initial cell concentration seeded was 6000 cell/cm². At day two, culture medium was removed and fresh medium was added. At day 5 live/death viability/cytotoxicity assay (ThermoFisher scientific) was performed. Gelatine and Matrigel coating conditions when used where performed as follows: 1% Gelatine was added to the flask/dish surface and was incubated 30 min into the cell incubator, after that gelatine was eliminated and cell were seeded. Matrigel was added to the surface flask and was incubated for 1h at 37°C. After that, three PBS washes were performed before seeding the cells.

Schneider 2 cell line

Schneider 2 cells (S2 cells) were cultured at 25°C in Schneider's medium supplemented with 2% FBS and 0,01% penicillin. We took cells from a confluent flask and seeded them on top of the different substrates in 1ml of medium, in a 1:10 dilution. They were then incubated at 25°C in culture medium for 2 days. After the culture we fixed the cells with a 4% paraformaldehyde solution for 40 minutes and stained with the nuclear specific fluorescent probe DAPI (1:1000 dilution) to efficiently count the cells attached to the substrates. Each experimental condition had three replicates.

Cells were imaged under a LEICA fluorescence microscope and counted using the FIJI-software.

Cell viability studies

LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity assay allows two-colour discrimination of live from dead populations based on membrane integrity, esterase activity, metabolic activity, or structural segmentation. Plasma membrane integrity is determined by ethidium homodimer-1 which enters cells with a compromised plasma membranes to bind DANN and emit a red fluorescence; live cells are identified by Calcein AM, a fluorogenic cell-permeant dye that is converted to a green fluorescence after interaction with intracellular esterase's.

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) assay

As a strong correlation between ROS and cell viability have been described, we measured ROS in cells cultured on nanopillar devices. 5(6)-Carboxy-2',7'-dichlorofluorescein diacetate (Carboxy-H2DCFDA) (ThermoFisher) is an acetylated and chemically reduced fluorescein form that is used as an indicator of ROS in cells. As a positive control, we used trans-o-hydroxybenzylidenepyruvate hydratase-aldolase (THBP) at 250µM. The probe was added to the cells at final concentration of 20µM, for 40 min at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Then, fluorescence was measured at λEx: 485nm - λEm: 527nm after 3-6h.

Wing imaginal discs

Oxidative stress in biological tissues is associated to the initial phases of cell damaging. A TREdsRED *Drosophila melanogaster* strain was used [11] for oxidative stress evaluation. This strain consists of a construct that is sensitive to proteins that are activated upon oxidative stress and bind to response elements in the DNA that will trigger transcription of the red fluorescent protein dsRED. In summary, cells under oxidative stress, will be distinguished by the red fluorescence. Flies were raised at 17°C and late L3 larvae were dissected in PBS 1x to isolate the wing imaginal discs. The wing discs were transferred to preheated (25°C) Schneider's culture medium, supplemented with 2% of heat-inactivated FBS, 1,25% Fly extract (VDRC, Vienna) and 5µg/ml insulin. The discs were cultured at 25°C for 24 hours and images were taken at timepoints 0, 3, 7 and 24. Only the nubbin region of the disc was used for quantification of the fluorescence.

For the confocal images, a LEICA SPE confocal laser scanning microscope was used. Data for mean pixel intensity were acquired using FIJI-software.

Statistical analysis was performed using a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a Tukey's post-hoc test to make comparisons between each group. Significance is indicated in the figures only when P<0.05, as follows: *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0,001.

Ex vivo model

This *ex-vivo* assay is based on precision-cut thin slices of fresh tumor samples obtained from surgical lung cancer patients. Fresh biopsies from surgical lung cancer patients were obtained with a protocol approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Clinic de Barcelona (CB/2019/0282) with the informed patient consent. Inclusion criteria are: surgical patient with diagnosed ADC/SCC, primary tumor size ≥ 1.5 cm, ≥ 18 -years-old, ECOG-PS 0-1, no previous systemic therapy or radiation, no intercurrent active infectious disease and signed informed consent. Both males and females will be included. Tumor biopsies were cut into thin small tissue fragments and laid on the nanodevice surface for 10 min to allow tissue attachment. Then, tumor fragments were covered with an optimized culture medium for 48h. As a control we used data from our standard *ex-vivo* protocol based on laying tumor fragments on Transwell inserts covered with the same optimized culture medium.

Analysis of tumor fragments was done by immunohistochemistry (IHC). In brief, *ex-vivo* samples were formalin fixed, paraffin embedded, and histologically analyzed through staining of hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and markers of cancer cell growth (KI-67) and fibroblast activation (α -SMA, picrosirius red). Each marker was quantified as a function of time either as cell number, percentage (%) positive nuclei or % of positive area as needed, using quPath.

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